

THE AGE OF TRANSFORMATIONS

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Technological changes have affected every part of our lives over the last few decades. From tapes to music apps, flip phones to video calls, TV to over-the-top (OTT) services, typewriters to voice typing, and light rail to metro rail, to name a few. This is because technology keeps getting better over time. The social networking site Facebook reached 100 million users in nine years, but ChatGPT did it in just two months. This shows how much faster things are changing.

As 2023 comes to a close, let's have a look at the opinions and predictions of technologists, media experts, and academics regarding how technology will change over the following decades. A lot of people are expected to use AR and VR at large in the next 20 years. AR is a short form of "augmented reality." AR is already deployed in online games like Pokemon Go. It uses a camera to take pictures of the real world and then turns them into a digital world. In the future, Google Maps will move you as if it has held your finger with the help of augmented reality.

Virtual reality is what VR stands for. Pilots are currently trained in virtual skies using this method. With VR in the future, we'll be able to walk through the Museum halls of another town or country and feel like we're really there. This still takes place in some ways today. For fun, there are concerts, sports games, school, travel, meetings, doctor's visits, and more. VR will be able to manage many such things.

According to Jeremy Goldman, CEO of Firebrand Group and author of "Going Social," voice instructions will be used for many mundane tasks. Technologies like Siri and Alexa will seem very basic compared to what's coming next. The way the breaking news is presented will change totally. Corey Bergman, co-founder of Breaking News, says that many witnesses will post hundreds of videos of the incident. We will be able to watch this information as if we were actually there on the scene. If there is an accident, someone watching the news will feel like he is there.

Smart watches will be able to do most of the things that only mobile phones can do today. People will start to use gadgets that can be worn. The head of 'Simply Measured', Otis Kimze, talks about the future of social media and how it might be built into clothes, glasses, or shoes. Like now, you won't have to take the gadgets along with you. They'll be on your clothes, buttons or at any suitable place. By hitting a particular spot, you can use your hand or palm like a phone. Astonishing? Well, a few decades ago, it seemed impossible to make a video call, which is a routine for us now.

Biometric technology is updating drastically. Holograms, which are 3D images of a person, would be able to attend the meetings on your behalf. Elon Musk owns 'NeuroLink Corporation', which is working on this neurotechnology. Another thing the company is working on is a brain-machine interface (BMI) that can be put inside a person's body. Adaptable technology will stay. Facebook is the most popular social networking platform right now. It holds about 3 billion accounts all over the world. It will live on, but it might look different. Some websites will only last for a certain amount of time. In a few years, the word "tweet" might be old-fashioned. Blogs, short films, and live videos will all be there. Stories and Status will become more popular and essential ways of one-to-many communication. It will have features that make it look great and vibrant.

Social media will continue to affect the world positively as well as negatively. An uprising for democracy began in Tunisia in December 2010. People in charge of Tunisia, Egypt, and Libya had to step down because of the unrest. Many people were able to protest and fight back against injustice with the help of Twitter and other social media sites. Critical social issues got a louder voice through hashtag movements like "Black Lives Matter" and "Me Too." Such trends will start on a larger scale in the future.

It's also more likely that social media will be destructive. It is found that most of the terrorist attacks are planned through social media groups that are quickly deleted once the work is done. These things are likely to increase in future with the help of AI and new tools. We can control this only if we can handle the fake accounts in time, which is not easy. Around the world, social media is already taking people to unrealistic illusions. The happiness is now proportional to the number of likes. It is getting scary with the increased trolling. This will go up by a considerable amount.

Your computer keeps track of who you are, what you look at, and how much time you spend on each page while you browse. This is called User Mapping. Based on what you like, it figures out what ads to show you on social media that are linked to your feed. For example, if you talk about "vacation" or "holiday" in a chat, email, or phone call, travel companies will start sending you ads. Based on this method, it will get worse from now on. You will be watched at all times. Insurance, banking, e-commerce, travel, entertainment, and other areas will buy more of that information. There will be a more significant breach of your privacy.

It will become much easier to cause chaos in society in the future by spreading fake news and pictures and taking advantage of people through blackmail, mental torture, and financial extortion. It will become more violent with the help of technology. With A-I, more deep fakes will be used. Since the human brain doesn't quickly figure it out, it could end up being like Pandora's box, full of deep fakes and dark web tunnels. Global regulatory bodies must take strict action as soon as possible to prevent harm to public health.

AI (artificial intelligence) will make it hard to be creative. Social media will make it harder for people to understand and analyze things. Emotions in people will also get messy and rough. The next step is that IBM has patented a way to keep memory on a chip in the brain. This chip makes it possible to remember and process new thoughts. It will be easy to bring back memories from the past. It might be helpful for patients with dementia or similar problems. Although it's also possible to hack into the memory, the aftereffects are beyond prediction at present.

Conclusion

To get ahead in any area, information alone is not enough; you also need knowledge. We need to learn and improve many skills. It's too bad that people have used technology without knowing how to use it. Everyone needs to decide how much AI and social media they need or should depend on. For instance, Nitin Gadkari, the Minister of Road Transport and Highways, has said that even though India has adopted new technologies, AI-powered self-driving cars will not be allowed to run in India. The lakhs of drivers need their jobs, and let's not allow AI to replace them. In a nutshell one needs to be Media literate. It will help him to understand and critically evaluate content across diverse media platforms. This will also help society to be equipped to navigate the complex landscape of modern information and Technology.

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